

Julian Mutter, Clemens Riegler and Hakan Kayal

The Idea

Autorotation for small payload landing

Samara-like autorotation systems can be dropped from landers. They are **controllable**, so can each land at a specified location. Using a spike at the bottom, they can **penetrate the ground** and remain in an **upright position** after landing.

The systems can **communicate** with each other. Each can host small and lightweight **payloads** to collect data during flight and on the ground. This allows the distribution of **sensor- and communication networks** on Mars and Earth.

The prototype

The prototype features a **lightweight wing** of around 15x40cm size. Attached is a **solid body** hosting the flight **electronics**, the **payloads** and a **servo motor** for actuating the wing. The prototype has shown to **successfully enter autorotation** without actuation needed.

The Simulation

6-DOF Simulation of the flight

The flight of the autorotation system is modeled in a **6-DOF** simulation which, starting from a slowly rotating system, can predict its flight. This consists of a phase where rotation rate and vertical velocity are increasing and then a phase of **stable autorotation** where these values stay constant. The model is used for the **development of control algorithms** for the autorotation system.

Validation of the simulation

These plots compare the simulation with data from **drop experiments** of the prototype from **30m** altitude, starting from the first time the vehicle was rotating faster than **4Hz**. They show that the transition from this starting rotation to **stable autorotation** is correctly predicted. The deviations in the predicted velocity of up to 1m/s are due to irregularities in real flight, caused by, e.g., wind.

Applicability to Mars

Comparison of Earth vs Mars

Conducting the simulation for a drop altitude of **100m** for **different wing lengths** for Earth and Mars shows that on Mars **similar vertical velocities** are **possible** as on Earth by simply increasing the size of the wing.

Possible payloads for Mars

- During flight, **barometers** can create a **vertical profile** of the atmosphere
- Distributed over an area, **atmospheric sensors** can provide data about the development of wind fields and other **weather phenomena**
- **Navigation beacons** can enable **positioning** of mobile systems on Mars
- **Communication relays** allow the communication of exploration systems in large areas
- Sensors in the spike of the autorotation system can analyze the **martian soil**
- **Cameras** can provide images during flight as well as on the ground

Sources

Riegler C. et al. "Project Daedalus: Towards Autorotation based Landing and Descent." 71st IAC Proceedings. 2020.
 Riegler, Clemens, Julian Mutter, and Hakan Kayal. "Comparison of autorotation and propulsive landing for planetary exploration." Acta Astronautica 234 (2025): 26-40.
 Mehringer, Johanna, et al. "Suborbital autorotation landing demonstrator on REXUS 29." 4th Symposium on Space Educational Activities. Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, 2022.
 Riegler Clemens, Lennart Werner, and Hakan Kayal. "MAPLE: Martian Autorotation Probe Lander Experiment." 2022.
 Mutter Julian, "Modeling and simulation of a propulsive landing system with 3DOF" 2023.
 Win, Shane Kyi Hla, et al. "The effects of chordwise wing optimization of single-winged samara in autorotation." 2017 IEEE Conference on Advanced Intelligent Mechatronics (AIM). IEEE, 2017.

